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Strengthening the Quality of Graduates in Dealing with the Asian Economic Community and Demographic Bonuses

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to describe the learning outcomes that graduates needed to face AEC and demographic bonuses. The data used in this article from the research result held in the Department of Anthropology Education of Universitas Negeri Medan. This research was conducted in the Sociology Subject Teachers' Meeting. This research is descriptive using data collection techniques through Forum Group Discussion (FGD). Mapping the ability of teachers needed by the graduates of the Department of Anthropology Education in dealing with the Asian Economic Community (AEC) and demographic bonuses. The graduates need to master two things in dealing with AEC, namely mastery of technology and mastery of knowledge.

Keywords: Learning Outcomes, Graduates' Ability, Demographic Bonuses, Technology

1. Introduction

Given that the education sector is a product that has the potential to be developed as a product with high competitiveness, the learning achievement of high school graduates must be able to answer the challenges of the period. Based on the results of the 2010 census the Government made population projections for 2020 and 2035. The projection results show that in 2020 there will be a change in population structure in Indonesia. The age group 0-4 years begins to decrease due to a decrease in the number of births. The age group of 5-9 years will experience swelling due to the high number of births from the previous 10 years and the population of the 65 years and above also increases.

The Indonesian National Qualifications Framework mandates that all learning outcomes set in the study program must refer to the needs of the business world and the industrial world. Therefore, the establishment of a curriculum at the Anthropology Education study program level must be based on tracer study results and input from professional associations and be able to answer the challenges of graduates in their time. The AEC and bonus demographics that are coming and continuing to approach are the conditions that will be faced by all college graduates in Indonesia, including study program graduates of Anthropology Education of Universitas Negeri Medan in the future (Malau, 2012).

Responding to this, the Study Program of Anthropology Education must be able to prepare prospective graduates to face all possibilities that will be faced in the future. Learning Outcomes are capabilities acquired through the internalization of knowledge, attitudes, skills, competencies, and accumulated work experience. In other words, the learning achievement can also be referred to as a measure of one's acquisition in analyzing the learning process both structured and unstructured. A research report conducted by the Institute for Strategy and Competitiveness, Harvard Business School, Indonesian products has strong global competitiveness, namely fisheries, agriculture, furniture, forestry, apparel, and footwear products. While other products such as education have the potential to be developed to have competitiveness in the global market (Ridhwan et al., 2015)

Starting from the description, this study tries to pass through the formulation of learning outcomes obtained by anthropology education students when they finish their undergraduate education in accordance with the profile of graduates determined by the Study Program of Department of Anthropology Education. Based on the background described earlier, the identified problems encountered are as follows:

1. Challenges faced by study program graduates. Anthropology education in the AEC period and the demographic bonus will be bigger and tighter
2. College graduates must be able to face the challenges faced in their time
3. The need to adjust the learning outcomes of study program graduates. Anthropology education faces the challenges of the AEC and the demographic bonus
4. There is a need for capacity mapping needed by Sociology or Anthropology and Integrated Social Studies teachers in facing the challenges of the AEC and demographic bonuses.

Based on the identification of the problems described, formulated the problem statement as follows:

1. What is the ability of integrated Sociology / Anthropology and Social Sciences teachers in the Sociology Subject Teacher Discussion?
2. What abilities are needed by study program graduates? Anthropology Education to become a teacher of Sociology / Anthropology and Integrated Social Sciences during the AEC and demographic bonuses?

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. Identify what abilities are needed by Sociology and Integrated Social Studies teachers to face AEC and demographic bonuses
2. Formulate learning outcomes of study program graduates. Anthropology Education.

Achievement of learning as stated in the Guidelines for Preparation of Learning Outcomes of Study Program Graduates is a formulation of learning objectives to be achieved and must be owned by all graduates, also a statement of the quality of graduates (Dirjen, Kemahasiswaan, Kementerian, & Kebudayaan, 2014). Learning Outcomes can be used by study programs as a direction to achieve the quality target of graduates that must be achieved. Descriptions of learning outcomes include knowledge, attitudes, skills, competencies, and accumulated work experience. 4 elements in the formulation of learning outcomes are attitudes and values, workability, mastery of knowledge, and authority and responsibility. Each element of Learning Outcomes in Graduate Competence Standard as stated in the Guidance is interpreted as follows:

1. Attitude is right and cultured behavior as a result of internalization and actualization of values and norms reflected in spiritual and social life through the learning process, student work experience, research, and/or community service related to learning.
2. Knowledge is systematic mastery of concepts, theories, methods, and/or philosophies in certain fields of science which are obtained through reasoning in the learning process, student work experience, research and/or community service related to learning. What is meant by student work experience is experience in activities in a particular field for a certain period of time in the form of work training, practical work, fieldwork practices or other similar types of activities.
3. Skills are the ability to perform performance using concepts, theories, methods, materials, and/or instruments, which are obtained through learning, student work experience, research and/or community service related to learning.

The skill element is divided into two namely general skills and special skills which are interpreted as follows:

- a) *General skills are general work abilities that must be possessed by each graduate in order to guarantee the equality of graduates' abilities according to the program level and type of higher education; and*
- b) *Special skills are special work abilities that must be possessed by each graduate in accordance with the scientific field of the study program.*

The main problem of education in Indonesia today, is the less effective of teaching in the education process in schools, caused by the following problem: (1) cost of education, this is the primary problem of education in this country, namely the high cost of education from basic to advanced level, this is appearing a lot phenomenon of dropping out of school among Indonesian children. Let alone for private schools, for public schools too, the cost of education remains high, School Operational assistance options provided by the government are still not able to overcome the problem of the high cost of this education; (2) lack of educational equality in Indonesia for some people, education is common, but for many people in remote areas, education is very luxury and valuable, because, in a country that embraces decentralization of irony, education is more focused on the more potential core areas, this causes less equity and makes the gap in education; (3) low-quality education facilities and infrastructure, we would have heard a lot of news about schools collapsed, or schools damaged because the building that have weathered but did not get help from the government, this is one proof of how low the quality of educational facilities and infrastructure in Indonesia; and (4) the low achievement of students from research and development, the ability of students to capture material in Indonesia only about 30% of all the material taught. this is influenced by many factors, such as lack of awareness in the world of education and also still lack of knowledge of students about the meaning of education (Ahmad, 2017)

The presence of qualified teachers is one of the hopes amid efforts to improve the quality of education. Qualified teachers are expected to be able to carry out their responsibilities properly and correctly. Not only that teachers are expected to be able to prepare students to face the challenges faced in their time. Colleges such as Medan State University must be able to present solutions by producing quality teachers. Therefore, the seriousness of universities such as Medan State University in producing quality teachers is needed at this time.

Based on the things mentioned above, identification of the abilities needed by students to face challenges in the future needs to be taken seriously. Revisions to the competencies needed by students need to be improved in accordance with the development and needs of their time.

2. Method

Based on the purpose, this study uses qualitative methods with focus group discussion as a technique of data collection. Participants in the focus group discussion are informants or informants consisting of lecturer representatives and associations associated with graduates. This research was conducted in several stages, namely: (i) inventory of problems, (ii) Focus Group Discussion with topics: competencies needed by teachers in facing ASEAN Economic Communities, (iii) Focus Group Discussion with topics: Profile of graduates and Learning Outcomes, and (iv) analysis of the Focus Group Discussion results

Inventory of problems aims to record the problems related to the challenges needed by graduates in facing the times of the ASEAN Economic Community. Inventory is carried out through a literature study of various published research results. The results of the inventory carried out are used as material for focus group discussions conducted in two stages. Focus Group Discussion invited various representatives from various associations related to graduates and lecturers of Study Programs of Anthropology Education. All information obtained from discussion participants was analyzed to get recommendations on revisions to graduate profiles and learning outcomes.

The data analysis used in this study is a qualitative descriptive analysis. The analysis technique is carried out by compiling a matrix of linkages of capabilities needed with predictions of challenges faced in the MEA period and demographic bonuses. Presentation of the results of data analysis is displayed in the form of narratives, and tables.

3. Result and discussion

The ASEAN economic community will shape ASEAN as a single market and production base, making a region more dynamic and competitive with mechanisms and steps to strengthen the implementation of new economic initiatives, accelerate regional integration in priority sectors, facilitate the movement of businesses, personnel skilled and talented work, and strengthening institutional mechanisms as a first step towards realizing the ASEAN Economic Community. An inventory of problems finds several problems that will be faced by graduates in the ASEAN Economic Community. These problems are related to the competencies needed by teachers in facing challenges in the era of the ASEAN Economic Community (Darmoko, 2016)

The teacher's professional competence describes the abilities that must be possessed by someone who is in charge of a position as a teacher, meaning that the ability displayed is a feature of his professionalism (Usman, 2000). The statement emphasizes that the ability possessed by the teacher is the key to the success of the teacher in carrying out his/her responsibilities in educating and preparing students to face future problems.

The first Focus Group Discussion discussed the competencies needed by teachers in facing the ASEAN Economic Community. The discussion was attended by study program lecturers. Anthropology Education, Universitas Negeri Medan. In the discussion obtained some understanding of the need for revisions to the curriculum implemented in the study program. The Department of Anthropology Education in an effort to prepare graduates to face challenges in the era of the ASEAN Economic Community.

Recognized by participants in the discussion of material mismatches even the courses on competencies needed by graduates (prospective teachers) were one of the reasons for the formation of the Teacher Education Program. The existence of the Teacher Education Program has eliminated the authority of the education program at the College in providing teaching certificates to graduates of Bachelor of Education. In this first Focus group discussion, it was also agreed on the profile of graduates produced by the Anthropology Education Study Program. Based on the results of the discussion and the tracer study, it was agreed that several profiles of graduates were teachers, social workers, and research assistants in social and cultural fields.

Competition for workers, especially Social Education subject teachers in schools, is believed by the discussion participants to soon become apparent. Therefore improving the quality of competency of prospective teachers produced by educational programs is very important. Improving the quality of teacher candidates' competencies is only possible if there is a change in the curriculum of the education study program so that graduates (prospective teachers) have high competitiveness (Darmoko, 2016).

Learning outcomes is a description that is used as a tool to map skills or careers or what is also called a graduate profile and develop curriculum. The achievement of graduate learning and competency standards of graduates of the department should be adjusted to the competency needs needed by graduate users. These competency needs always change according to the times. Departments must be able to prepare graduates to face the challenges that graduates will face when they graduate.

The process of developing and preparing curriculum for a department must be continued by determining the competency standards of graduates and the standard of learning content. Graduates Competency Standards are the minimum criteria for graduate qualifications which include attitudes, knowledge, and skills. Whereas the standard of learning content is a minimum criterion for the level of depth and breadth of learning material. The role of professional associations related to majors becomes very important in the preparation of graduate competency standards and standards of learning content. Information about the profession of alumni from majors can help majors develop the curriculum according to the competency needs needed by graduate users. This information can also be used as input for those who are future graduates. Based on the discussion that developed in the focus group discussion, it was agreed that the second and third graduate profile competencies must be adjusted to the applicable laws and regulations.

The period of the ASEAN Economic Community will be accompanied by the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 which was marked by the development of the digital era. Industrial Revolution 4.0 demands all fields to

master digital technology. So, the mastery of technology is also a competency that must be owned by prospective teachers, especially teachers of Social Sciences subjects. There are three important abilities that must be possessed by professional teachers, namely; professional, personal or personality, social, and pedagogical competence (Darmoko, 2016). Professional competence requires teachers to have extensive and in-depth knowledge of the fields of study being taught, and methodological mastery in terms of having knowledge of theoretical concepts, being able to choose the right method and being able to use it in the teaching and learning process. This competency requires the teacher to have a solid and commendable personality attitude, as Ki Hajar Dewantoro teaches, namely *Ing ngarso sung tulodho* means that in front of you becomes a role model, *ing madya mangun karso* means in the middle build intentions, *tut wuri handayani* means behind giving moral support.

Social competence means that a teacher must have good social communication skills, with students, with fellow teachers, with principals and employees, as well as with the community. Pedagogic competence is the ability in the management of students which includes: (1) understanding insight or educational foundation; (2) understanding of students; (3) development of curriculum or syllabus; (4) learning planning; (5) implementing learning that is educational and dialogical; (6) evaluation of learning outcomes; (7) developing students to actualize their various potentials. Focus Group Discussion agreed on two major needs by graduates (prospective teachers), namely; mastery of technology and mastery of knowledge.

Table 1 Matrix of Graduates' Need and Learning Outcomes

<i>Graduates' Need</i>	<i>Learning Outcome</i>
Mastery of Technology	Managing resources, technology, implementing minimum professional standards equivalent, evaluating, strategic development of the organization.
Mastery of Knowledge	mastery of the application theory of knowledge and skills related to his duties as a teacher who will face the ASEAN economic community

Discussions on the need for mastery of technology agree on some of the learning outcomes needed, namely; managing resources, technology, implementing minimum professional standards that are equal, evaluating, strategic development of the organization. Mastery of knowledge requires graduates to achieve a number of things, namely mastering the theory of application of knowledge and skills related to their duties as teachers who will face the ASEAN economic community.

Technology will be a resource in various aspects of life including education. Therefore the learning outcomes needed in managing technology resources are an important part of fulfilling a teacher's professionalism in the future, given the technological developments that cannot be avoided in the future. Not one teacher can survive in the future without having the ability to master technology.

The ability to evaluate the learning program that has been implemented is intended so that the teacher is able to develop a learning program that fits the needs of his students in the future. Successful teachers are teachers who are able to prepare their students to face the challenges faced by their students in the present and future. Mastery of knowledge in the subjects that are utilized becomes an unchanging ability. This is due to the views of participants who still assess the importance of the role of teachers as verifiers of knowledge obtained by students.

4. Conclusion

The learning outcome of graduates of the Department of Anthropology Education is must be upgraded to level 7 of the Indonesian National Qualifications Framework. This result could be used as a recommendation for any department to update the learning outcomes.

References

- Ahmad, Y. B. (2017). Management of Quality-Based Education in Facing Asian Economic, *128* (first edition), 172–175.
- Darmoko, P. D. (2016). Peran strategis guru dalam mea. *Jurnal Madaniyah*, *1*, 143–156.
- Dirjen, Kemahasiswaan, P., Kementerian, D. P. T., & Kebudayaan. (2014). Capaian Pembelajaran Lulusan Program Studi.
- Malau, M. T. M. (2012). Aspek Hukum Peraturan Dan Kebijakan Pemerintah Indonesia. *Rechtsvinding*, *1*(2 Agustus), 375–395.
- Ridhwan, M. M., Wicaksono, G., Nurliana, L., Bary, P., Suryani, F. T., & Satyanugroho, R. (2015). Working Paper Industri Nasional Di Era Masyarakat Ekonomi Asean Dan Perdagangan Bebas.
- Usman, M. U. (2000). *Menjadi Guru Profesional*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.